

The Momentum Probabilistic Nature of Quantum Bound States

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Quantum mechanics is used to solve for the probabilistic 2-slit interference and one dimensional reflection-refraction, because classical mechanics cannot solve these problems. It is not that there is no motion in time in these problems, but rather that probability is involved and one may solve them using a time independent probability. One must perform multiple runs in time in order to experimentally determine the statistical probabilities and even physical results obtained using $\exp(ipx)$. A time independent probabilistic approach using $\exp(ipx)$ predicts these results because it is akin to a steady stream scenario.

Classical bound states, however, are deterministic. There is no probability so why should quantum mechanics apply to these? In order for these states to be deterministic, one must have a different p at each dx at x , with dx shrinking to 0 for a given $V(x)$. In other words, one requires infinite x resolution. The above probabilistic cases, however, follow from $\exp(ipx)$ which suggests a minimum x spatial resolution region, \hbar/p . In other words, there is uncertainty in this region or probability. Thus, a quantum probabilistic treatment applies if in fact resolution \hbar/p is large compared to dx classical. If it is not, there is no probability and there is nothing wrong with a classical mechanical analysis, we argue. The quantum treatment, however, does not follow a particle in time, but rather considers all different times together and uses $\exp(ipx)$ s. It leads to a set of crests and troughs (e.g. oscillator) which yield an overall spatial resolution with time resolution given by \hbar/E_n . Thus, for large crest trough bases compared to dx , there is no following of a particle in time. Quantum mechanics describes the probabilistic nature of this problem. The question is how?

We suggest that in a classical bound state, there is a specific p and $pp/2m$ (nonrelativistic) for each dx . The particle spends a time, $dt=dx/v(x)$ in each $dt(x)$ and so one might argue that this is a probability weight such that $dt(x)/T E$ is the amount of energy linked with a particular p . In other words, we suggest that a state is described by p and for $dt(x)/T E$, one does not really need to know x if one knows $dt(x)/T$. It is simply a number linked with p .

We try to apply these same considerations to the bound state treated quantum mechanically. Such a state is probabilistic because of \hbar/p , but one still wants to use momentum to define a state. $\exp(ipx)$, however, exists in all of space, but is orthogonal to $\exp(ip_1x)$ and so one may integrate $\sum a(p)^* \exp(-ipx)$ against the average energy associated with $\exp(ipx)$. What is this energy? First of all, $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with $pp'/2m$ (nonrelativistically). Thus, $pp/2m \exp(ipx)$ is an average kinetic energy, albeit using an unusual probability.

What about the potential? If one considers momentum as defining the state, then one must have momentum collisions. If $V(x)$ renders a k momentum hit, then this must be associated with a probability of $\exp(ikx)$. There is some energy linked to this $\exp(ikx)$. To find this, one may use: $V(x)=\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. Before a reaction, to see a momentum of p , one may consider $\sum_k V_k a(p-k) \exp(ikx) \exp(ipx)$. This energy, should be proportional to $dt(x)/T$, i.e. $a(p)a(p)E$ so $pp/2m a(p) + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) = E a(p)$ because one multiplies by W^* . This probabilistic treatment serves to determine the $a(p)$ weights and the E_n values.

In the high E_n limit, \hbar/p becomes tiny compared to dx and there is no probability, so there is no need for quantum mechanics, we argue. One may, however, mathematically consider W

with a high E_n . This W , however, is a statistical object and is not linked with motion in time. One may replace its predictions with a deterministic theory, classical mechanics, because there is no longer any probability. Thus, there is no reason, we argue, for the statistical quantum mechanical picture using $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ to decouple $\exp(ipx)$ s at high E_n . It is simply a statistical picture which mixes different times together to make predictions. In the high E_n limit, these predictions must match $x(t)$ analysis (deterministic).

Quantum Mechanics and Probability

Classical mechanics is deterministic and follows a particle in time because there is no probability. If there were some probability in the situation, one would have to know the distribution a priori, but it is actually the case that one wants the theory to provide this distribution. For example for 2-slit interference and one dimensional reflection-refraction, probability is key, but one cannot measure it without making many repeated time runs. In order to have a theory which predicts the probability distribution, one needs to pull time out of the picture and consider different possible scenarios (which physically occur at different times) together. For example, for one dimensional reflection-refraction, the particle or photon either reflects or refracts, but one considers the two events together in space with no time. Similarly, for 2-slit interference, one considers probability to pass through one slit or the other together even though physically one may occur at a time. The probability used is $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, the quantum treatment is not one which follows the particle in time, but uses probabilities in space.

Bound State

A classical mechanical bound state is deterministic and follows a particle in time. It was argued that quantum mechanics with $\exp(ipx)$ deals with probabilities. Why should quantum mechanics be applied to a bound state?

$\exp(ipx)$, the free particle probability or wavefunction, is a probability which conserves momentum (1). It is linked with a wavelength, \hbar/p , and one cannot determine matters without probability within this wavelength. That is fine if $\hbar/p \ll dx$, but otherwise is a problem because one has a probabilistic theory.

How should one treat the bound state in quantum mechanics? If $\exp(ipx)$ is the probability linked with p and $p^2/2m$, then $p^2/2m \exp(ipx)$ is a kind of average probability. Like with the classical situation, momentum defines a state, but this has a wavelength of \hbar/p . The quantum approach is to remove time and so one has a set of two dimensional crests-troughs representing a free particle at all times. This clearly is not the $x(t)$ approach of classical mechanics, but is the quantum probabilistic one.

If $dt(x)/T E$ is the energy linked with a given p classically (which exists at a dx at x), then to mimic this quantum mechanically, one would want energies linked with p values again, but now p is associated with $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. p may exist anywhere in space. This is a statistical treatment of the problem and suggests that $V(x)$ is represented by k momentum hits. These must be linked with $\exp(ikx)$ because there is momentum conservation and $\exp(ikx)$ is the probability which delivers this. One does not know the energy linked with k , but can find it using $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$.

In (1), we suggested that if two particles collide (p_1, p_2) to create (p_3, p_4), then one uses $\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)$ before and $\exp(-ip_3x-ip_4x)$ after. Here, one only needs the energy before and so nonrelativistically:

$$p^2/2m a(p) \exp(ipx) + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) \exp(ipx) = a(p) E \exp(ipx) \quad ((1))$$

This is orthogonal to other $\exp(ip_1x)$ s and so one may $W^*(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(-ipx)$ and multiply with ((1)) and integrate over x . This should then give $dt(x)/T E$.

The use of the quantum approach is that it yields the $a(p)$, the spatial resolution profile and the E_n values. ΔE_n may then be checked experimentally.

High E_n Limit

We have argued that quantum mechanics ($\exp(ipx)$) is a probabilistic theory. There is only probability in a bound state if $\hbar/p > dx$, otherwise there is not. If there is no probability then a deterministic approach (classical mechanics) to finding $x(t)$ is fine. There is actually motion in time even in the quantum case, we argue, but there is also probability. The quantum case uses $\exp(ipx)$ with no time to consider different probability scenarios. Thus, one should not expect that this theory simply collapses into a time dependent one for high E_n . It doesn't because there is no time in the $\exp(ipx)$ picture. Furthermore, the quantum picture uses $\exp(ipx)$ s which exist for all x even for high E_n , while the classical mechanical approach only has one p for each x . The quantum rms p is the classical p at x . This, we argue, is fine because quantum mechanics is a statistical theory which makes predictions. In the high E_n limit, these predictions should be consistent with a scenario in which one follows a particle deterministically in time. There is no need to decouple p s in $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ for high E_n , we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the quantum mechanical free particle probability, $\exp(ipx)$, is introduced as a probability which leads to momentum conservation, albeit by creating orthogonal functions in x . $\exp(ipx)$ is used in motion through time problems which contain probability, such as the 2-slit experiment and one dimensional reflection-refraction. No time is considered only space, so one considers events occurring at different times in the same spatial equation. This then leads to a probability distribution which would be realized by repeating many time runs.

A bound state is usually considered to be deterministic. If, however, $\hbar/p > dx$, then one does not have a fixed p within a dx . We suggest that this is then probabilistic and requires an $\exp(ipx)$ approach which includes all $\exp(ipx)$ s (including for different times) and also all x points for a given p . This suggests a $V(x)$ which yields k impulse hits. This $V(x)$ must be linked with $\exp(ikx)$ for momentum conservation, but if $a(p)p^2/2m \exp(ipx)$ is the energy profile for a given p , then $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ should be the profile for potential energy. Like with the classical case, one may describe states by momentum p , but p states now exist in all of space. One

wishes to have non-interfering contributions from each so: $\{ \frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) \} \exp(ipx) = E_n a(p) \exp(ipx)$. This is equivalent to the time-independent Schrodinger equation and yields $a(p)$ and E_n values.

For high E_n , one sees that crest-trough base values become very small, i.e. less than dx . This means that there is no resolution issue anymore and that the problem is no longer probabilistic, but deterministic. One may thus follow the particle in time? What about the quantum approach? It is a statistical approach which should yield predictions. In the high E_n case, these predictions are consistent with the classical $x(t)$ approach. We suggest that one does not have to worry about decoupling $\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ because there is a fixed p at each x .

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Conservation of Momentum in Terms of Probability, Space, Time (preprint, zenodo, 2024)